

Binding studies of serum albumins with an anticancer drug 6-mercaptopurine : A spectroscopic analysis

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Abstract : Interactions of serum albumin (SA) with different drugs is an important topic of research in the field of biophysical chemistry. In this review 6-MP, an anticancer drug has been investigated with the help of different spectroscopic tools. The mode of interaction has been analyzed and finally docking with HSA has been given as an additional supporting information. From all the works it has been found that the main interaction of small 6-MP molecule with SAs has been primarily dynamic with a minor contribution from static component. Both thermodynamic parameters and docking studies revealed hydrophobic interaction to play the dominant role with domain II being the primary binding site.

Keywords : Serum albumin, 6-mercaptopurine, fluorescence quenching, molecular docking, binding parameters.

Abbreviations : 6-MP = 6-Mercaptopurine, BSA = Bovine Serum Albumin, HSA = Human Serum Albumin, CD = Circular dichroism, FRET = Förster resonance energy transfer.

Introduction

Recently considerable attention has been focused on the study of the interaction between small molecules (drugs) and biological macromolecules (e.g. plasma protein), especially discussing the thermodynamic quantity, binding parameters and conformational changes of proteins caused by drugs. Biomolecule-drug interaction plays an important role in medicinal chemistry and biology. Binding of drugs to plasma proteins is an important pharmacological parameter, since it frequently affects the distribution, elimination, delivery rate, pharmacological response, therapeutic efficiency and design of a drug¹. Moreover, the anticancer activity of many drugs may be strongly affected by drug-protein interactions in the blood stream²⁻⁴.

Serum albumins are the most abundant proteins in the circulatory system of a wide variety of organisms, being the major macromolecule contributing to the osmotic blood pressure. It is the major transport protein and is capable of binding many endogenous and exogenous drugs reversibly and it may aid in selective delivery of these studied drugs to tumour region and facilitate drug access into the cell. In addition to blood plasma, serum albumins are also found in tissues and bodily secretions throughout the body; the extravascular protein comprises 60% of the total albumin.

There are two types of serum albumins, Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) and Human Serum Albumin (HSA). HSA and BSA are extensively studied due to their significance in the pharmacology field. Serum albumins consist of amino acid chains forming a single polypeptide with well-known sequence, which contain three homologous domains (I-III) that assembled to form a heart shaped molecule. Each domain contains 10 helices and is divided into anti-parallel six-helix and four domains (A and B) extensively cross-linked by disulfide bridges (Structure 1, in Chart 1). The shape of serum albumins can be approximated to a solid equilateral triangle with sides of $\sim 80 \text{ \AA}$ and average depth of $\sim 30 \text{ \AA}$ ⁵.

Both HSA and BSA display approximately 80% sequence homology and a repeating pattern of disulfides. The molecular weights are 66 kDa for BSA and 66.5 kDa for HSA. The tertiary structures of HSA and BSA show 76% similarity⁶. Crystal structure analyses have revealed that HSA contains 585 amino acid residues with 17 tyrosyl residues and only one tryptophan (Trp) located at position 214 along the chain (subdomain IIA); whereas, BSA contains 582 amino acid residues with 20 tyrosyl residues and two tryptophans located at positions 134 and 212 and Trp-

Structure 1. Crystal structure of HSA, from Ref. 5.

Structure 2. Trp residues of (a) HSA and (b) BSA, from Ref.²¹.

Structure 3. 6-Mercaptopurine (6-MP).

Chart 1

134 at the surface of the molecule⁶⁻²⁰. The chemical microenvironment of Trp-212 in BSA is similar to that of Trp-214 in HSA. Structure 2 (Chart 1) shows the three dimensional structure of HSA and BSA with tryptophan residues marked by arrows²¹. The principal binding regions of albumin are located in subdomain IIA (the warfarin-azapropazone binding site, site I) and in subdomain IIIA (indole-benzodiazepine binding site, site II)^{22,23,25}. The binding affinity offered by site I involves hydrophobic interactions; whereas, site II involves a combination of hydrophobic, hydrogen binding, and electrostatic interactions^{5,24,36}.

Mercaptopurine (also called 6-mercaptopurine, 6-MP)

is an immunosuppressive medication. It is used to treat acute lymphocytic leukemia, acute myoblastic leukemia, chronic myelocystic leukemia, trophoblastic neoplasia, Crohn's disease, and ulcerative colitis. It is a thiopurine. Among the WHO model list of essential medicines, 6-MP is considered to be the most important medications needed in a basic health system. Recent research indicated that oral absorption of 6-MP is relatively low, and about 50% of the drug appears in the plasma in 1–2 h. Being an essential medicine it is important to see the interaction of this drug with serum albumin. The structure is given in Chart 1 (Structure 3).

The investigation of the binding of 6-MP with BSA and HSA has attracted a great attention and several spectroscopic studies on the interaction between 6-MP with BSA and HSA have been published^{26-30,46,47}. Spectroscopy techniques such as absorption, fluorescence, circular dichroism spectra (CD spectra) etc. are very sophisticated tools to investigate the interactions between the drug-protein systems, as these tools are very sensitive towards the microenvironments of the protein. Fluorescence spectroscopy is widely use as a sensitive and convenient method indicating the alteration of the fluorophore environment which can provide plenty of useful information. The aim of this review was to study interactions of BSA and HSA with 6-MP using UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy, fluorescence quenching method, CD spectra, Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET) and molecular docking, reveal their character and compare the results obtained by different authors on interaction of HSA and BSA with 6-MP.

2. Methods used

2.1. Absorption :

Absorption spectrum is an important tool to get an idea about the wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{\max}) of a system. In BSA-6-MP system, λ_{\max} of BSA and 6-MP occurs at 280 nm and 320 nm respectively, which can be seen from Fig. 1²⁷. An idea about the quenching type can oftenly predicted from the absorption curve, which has been discussed in Section 2.2.

2.2. Fluorescence quenching :

Fluorescence quenching gives us very important observations and informations about the microenvironment of the fluorophor and drug. The interacting molecule can

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of BSA in presence of 6-MP²⁷.

quench the fluorophore in three different way. Firstly, the quenching can occur without any red or blue shift, i.e. hydrophobicity and polarity of the microenvironment does not alter. Secondly, quenching can occur with a red shift of the spectrum, i.e. increase in polarity or decrease in hydrophobicity of the microenvironment and thirdly, quenching can occur with a blue shift of the spectrum which indicate the decrease in polarity or increase in hydrophobicity of the microenvironment^{24,31,32}. For example, the fluorescence of BSA quenched by 6-MP (Fig. 2) is accompanied by a red shift in the emission spectrum of BSA²⁷.

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of BSA in the presence of varying concentrations of 6-MP ($T = 298$ K). The inset corresponds to the Stern-Volmer plot²⁷.

The quenching of fluorescence can be described by the Stern-Volmer equation as follows :

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{SV}[Q] = 1 + K_q\tau_0 [Q] \quad (1)$$

where, F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively; K_q is the bimolecular quenching constant; τ_0 is the lifetime of the fluorophore in the absence of quencher, and Q is the concentration of quencher³³. The Stern-Volmer quenching constant is given by $K_D = K_q\tau_0$. If the quenching is known to be dynamic, the Stern-Volmer constant will be represented by K_D . Otherwise this constant will be described as K_{SV} . From eq. (1), K_{SV} can be obtained by linear regression of a plot of F_0/F against $[Q]$. For example, the classical Stern-Volmer plot for BSA in presence of 6-MP is shown in the inset of Fig. 2²⁷. The Stern-Volmer quenching constants for serum albumins by 6-MP are summarized in Table 1. From the K_q values we can get an idea about static quenching. The maximum value possible for diffusion-limited quenching in water is in the order of $10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ³⁴. When the value of the bimolecular quenching constant (K_q) is higher, it could mean that there is a complex formation between protein and quencher, corresponding to a static mechanism^{33,40}. The values of K_q are given in Table 1. Another form of Stern-Volmer method is :

$$\frac{RF_0}{\Delta RF} = \frac{1}{[L]} \cdot \frac{1}{f_a} \cdot \frac{1}{K_Q} + \frac{1}{f_a} \quad (2)$$

where, RF_0 and RF are the relative intensities of protein in absence and in presence of the quencher, respectively, f is the fractional maximum fluorescence intensity of protein summed up, K_Q is a quenching constant and $[L]$ is the quencher concentration²⁶. From eq. (2), K_Q can obtain

from the plot of $\frac{RF_0}{\Delta RF}$ vs $\frac{1}{[L]}$.

The fluorescence quenching process can either be of static or dynamic. Static quenching refers to the formation of a non-fluorescent ground-state complex between the fluorophore and quencher. When this complex absorbs light it immediately returns to the ground state without emission of a photon whereas, dynamic quenching refers to process where the fluorophore and the quencher interact during the excited-state lifetime of the fluorophore. The static and dynamic quenching can be distinguished by the absorption spectra, temperature dependence or by lifetime measurements of the fluorophore-quencher complex. For static quenching, the bimolecular quenching constant,

K_q , decreases with increase in temperature, due to the decrease in stability of the fluorophore-quencher complex with higher temperature, whereas; the bimolecular quenching constant increases with increase in temperature in case of dynamic quenching. Similarly, if the fluorescence lifetime of serum albumins remains same with increasing concentration of the quencher, the quenching process is said to be static; whereas, if the lifetime of serum albumin decreases with increase in quencher concentration, then the process is said to be dynamic. In the absorption curve, if there is no observation of change in absorption maxima with increasing concentration of 6-MP (i.e. red shift or blue shift), then it reveals that it follows the dynamic mechanism, as in dynamic quenching process the excited state is only affected, not the ground state; whereas, a change in the absorption maxima indicates a change in the ground state, hence the quenching follows the static mechanism. A third process, which involves both the static and dynamic quenching simultaneously, the observed nature of the plot between F_0/F vs $[Q]$ is an upward curvature³⁴. Another form of modified Stern-Volmer equation is³⁴ :

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{app}[Q] \quad (3)$$

where, K_{app} is the apparent quenching constant, $K_{app} = (F_0/F - 1)/[Q] = (K_D + K_S) + K_D K_S [Q]$ and K_S is the association constant for complex formation. If K_{app} is calculated for each quencher concentration, $[Q]$, then plot of K_{app} vs $[Q]$ results a straight line with a positive slope (S) of $K_D K_S$ and intercept (I) of $(K_D + K_S)$. The individual constants can be determined from the two solutions of the quadratic equation, $K_S^2 - K_S I + S = 0$, where, $I = (K_D + K_S)$ and $S = K_D K_S$.

Bi *et al.* and Sułkowska *et al.* found the quenching of BSA as well as red shift due to the addition of 6-MP to BSA solution and explained the fact due to bringing of the tryptophan residue to a more hydrophilic environment in the drug-protein system^{26,35}. The K_{SV} values obtained by Ehteshami *et al.* and Hu *et al.* from temperature variation studies of BSA-6-MP system (Table 1) reveals a steady increase in the K_{SV} values, which was explained as a result of dynamic collision mechanism, which existed in the interaction of 6-MP with BSA^{27,28}. Evidence from the absorption spectra about this dynamic quenching was given by Hu *et al.* They confirmed this by using the dif-

Table 1. The values of K_{SV} , τ_0 , K_q , K_b , n , ΔS , ΔH , ΔG at different temperatures of BSA-6-MP and HSA-6-MP interactions

	293 K	298 K	300 K	301 K	304 K	307 K	308 K	310 K	315 K	318 K
BSA	2.1958 ^[28]	7.61×10^{-3} [27]	2.27 ^[28]	7.7×10^{-3} [27]	7.9×10^{-3} [27]	7.99×10^{-3} [27]	2.33 ^[28]	8.11×10^{-3} [27]	2.40 ^[28]	-
K_{SV} (L/mol)	5×10^{-9} [34]	7.50×10^{-3} [29]	5×10^{-9} [34]	3.42×10^3 [26]	5×10^{-9} [34]	5×10^{-9} [34]	5×10^{-9} [34]	5×10^{-9} [34]	5×10^{-9} [34]	-
τ_0 (s)	4.4×10^8 [28]	1.5×10^6 [27]	4.5×10^8 [28]	1.5×10^6 [27]	1.58×10^6 [27]	1.6×10^6 [27]	4.7×10^8 [28]	1.6×10^6 [27]	4.8×10^8 [28]	-
K_q (L/mol/s)	-	1.5×10^6 [29]	-	6.8×10^{11} [26]	-	-	-	-	-	2.3×10^3 [26]
K_b (10^3 L/mol)	1.072 ^[28]	-	1.202 ^[28]	0.92 ^[26]	-	-	1.160 ^[28]	-	1.479 ^[28]	0.96 ^[26]
n	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ΔS (J/mol/K)	-	-	-	-	487.3 ^[28]	-	-	-	-	-
ΔH (kJ/mol)	-	-	-	-	225.5 ^[26]	-	-	-	-	-
ΔG (kJ/mol)	-17.84 ^[28]	-	-21.25 ^[28]	-19.4 ^[26]	124.926 ^[28]	-	-25.15 ^[28]	-	-28.56 ^[28]	-
K_{SV} (L/mol)	-	2.20×10^{-3} [29]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
K_b (L/mol)	-	1.80×10^{-3} [29]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

ference absorption spectroscopy to obtain spectra. The UV absorption spectrum in the near ultraviolet band (250–400 nm) of BSA (Fig. 1, curve C) and the difference absorption spectrum (Fig. 1, curve B) between BSA-6-MP and 6-MP at the same concentration could be superposed within experimental error, this result reconfirm that the probable quenching mechanism of fluorescence of BSA by 6-MP is a dynamic quenching procedure. Moreover, Bi *et al.* concluded the quenching process of BSA by 6-MP could be static and not dynamic from the K_q value²⁶. The K_q values for all K_{SV} values are not reported and hence we have calculated the values of K_q (Table 1), using the given K_{SV} values and standard τ_0 value, obtained from other papers. The natural lifetime for the biological macromolecules is generally given as 10^{-8} s^{35,38,39}. However, the value for BSA is more precisely estimated as 5 ns³⁴. By calculating the K_q values, we found that some values were less and some values were greater than 2.0×10^{10} L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, the maximum diffusion collision quenching rate constant. Hence the quenching process between the drug-protein systems could be static or dynamic. Taking into account these results, it seems that a dynamic quenching component in overall static quenching process is involved in the quenching of BSA fluorescence intensity by 6-MP²⁸.

2.3. Binding constant (K_b) and binding sites (n) :

Binding constant, K_b , and the number of binding sites, n , can be found out using the following equation for static quenching^{34,39-42} :

$$\log [(F_0 - F)/F] = n \log K_b - n \log (1/[Q_t] - \{(F_0 - F) [P_t]/F_0\}) \quad (4)$$

where, F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of the quencher, $[Q_t]$ and $[P_t]$ are the total quencher concentration and the total protein concentration, respectively. In this equation, the total concentration of quencher is used instead of the free concentration of quencher. According to eq. (4), K_b and n values can be obtained by the plot of $\log [(F_0 - F)/F]$ vs $\log (1/[Q_t] - (F_0 - F) [P_t]/F_0)$.

Another simple form of equation for determination of binding constant, modified Stern-Volmer equation is :

$$\log \frac{(F_0 - F)}{F} = \log K_b + n \log [Q] \quad (5)$$

where, K_b is the binding constant and n is the number of binding sites, F_0 is the fluorescence intensity of free protein and F is the consecutive fluorescence intensity on addition of the quencher. Plot of $\log (F_0 - F)/F$ against $\log [Q]$ was used to determine the values of K_b and n from the intercept and the slope respectively. A third method is the Scatchard method. The equation being :

$$\frac{[L_b]}{[L_f][X]} = nK_b - K_b \cdot \frac{[L_b]}{[X]} \quad (6)$$

where, $[L_f]$ and $[L_b]$ denotes concentration of free and bound ligands respectively and $[X]$ denotes the amount of protein or tryptophan concentration. Bi *et al.* has found that the K_b value increased with raise in temperature for BSA-6-MP system (Table 1), which they explained as a result of endothermic process²⁶.

2.4. Activation energy calculation :

Since, the K_{SV} values can be measured at different temperatures, one can calculate the activation energy value using Arrhenius equation (eq. (7)). The plot of $\ln K_{SV}$ vs $1/T$ (T , absolute temperature) was found to be linear which makes it possible to calculate the activation energy, E_a , for the quenching process using the Arrhenius equation :

$$\ln K_{SV} = \ln A - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (7)$$

where K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer quenching constant at corresponding temperature, T . E_a is the activation energy for the quenching process, the parameter A is called the frequency factor (or pre-exponential factor) and R is the gas constant. A least square fitting of these data points give the E_a value for 6-MP quenching. The value of E_a was found to be 4.26 kJ mol⁻¹ and 3.089 kJ mol⁻¹ by Hu *et al.* and Ehteshami *et al.* respectively^{27,28}.

2.5. Thermodynamic parameters and nature of the binding forces :

The interaction forces between a ligand and biomolecule may include hydrogen bond, van der Waals interactions, electrostatic, hydrophobic forces etc. The thermodynamic parameters of binding reaction could be used as the main evidence for confirming these acting forces. Therefore, thermodynamic parameters dependent on temperatures usually calculate by researchers to explain the interaction of 6-MP with serum albumins using the following equa-

tions (eqs. (8), (9), (10)). If temperature range does not change significantly, enthalpy change (ΔH) can be considered as a constant parameter. Therefore, using the following equations, intermolecular force types and the free energy change (ΔG) of 6-MP with BSA can be estimated :

$$\ln K_b = \Delta H/RT + \Delta S/R \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (9)$$

In these equations, R is the gas constant, T is the experimental temperature and K_b is the binding constant at the corresponding T . ΔH , ΔS and ΔG are enthalpy change, entropy change and free energy change respectively. ΔH and ΔS can be obtained from the plot of $\ln K_b$ vs $1/T$ in eq. (8). Another set of equations to calculate the thermodynamic parameters, when temperature variation can be done for the system, are :

$$\ln K_b = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_B \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{K_{b2}}{K_{b1}} = \frac{\Delta H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \quad (12)$$

The thermodynamic parameters for the interaction of 6-MP with BSA are listed in Table 1. A positive ΔS and ΔH reveals the fact that the binding is mainly entropy-driven and a hydrophobic effect contributes in the interaction between 6-MP and BSA²⁷. The negative sign for ΔG reveals that the binding process is spontaneous in the standard conditions.

2.6. Circular Dichroism (CD) :

Secondary structure of protein can be determined by CD spectroscopy in the far-UV spectral region (190–250 nm). At these wavelengths the chromophore is the peptide bond, and the signal arises when it is located in a regular, folded environment. Alfa-helix (α -helix), beta-sheet (β -sheet), and random coil structures each give rise to a characteristic shape and magnitude of CD spectrum⁴¹. The residue ellipticity, $[\theta]_{MRE}$ ($\text{deg cm}^2 \text{dmol}^{-1}$), can be calculated from the measured θ by using equation :

$$[\theta]_{MRE} = \frac{\theta \times 100 \times M_r}{c \times l \times N_A} \quad (13)$$

where, θ is the measured ellipticity in degrees, c is the protein concentration in mg/ml, l is the path length in cm, and M_r is the protein molecular weight, N_A is the number

of amino acids (585 amino acids calculated from the primary structure) per protein. CD spectrum of HSA exhibits two negative bands at 208 and 222 nm (Fig. 4), typical of an α -helix structure of the protein. The negative bands at 208 and 222 nm are rationalized by the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the peptide bond of α -helical. When the binding of a molecule to protein result in a decrease in negative

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plot of BSA-6-MP system²⁷.

Fig. 4. CD far-UV spectra of HSA in native state and in presence of 6-MP⁴³.

ellipticity at all wavelengths of the far-UV CD without any significant shift of the peaks, it indicates changes in the protein secondary structure, and decrease of the α -helix content in protein. The CD data can be used to determine the relative amounts of the secondary structural elements of a protein. The procedure is based on the approximation that a protein CD spectrum in the amide region can be represented as a linear combination of the contribution of the different elements of secondary struc-

ture, according to equation :

$$\theta(\lambda) = f_{\alpha} \times [\theta_{\alpha}(\lambda)] + [f_t \times [\theta_t(\lambda)] + f_n \times [\theta_n(\lambda)]] \quad (14)$$

where, $[\theta_{\alpha}(\lambda)]$, $[\theta_t(\lambda)]$ and $[\theta_n(\lambda)]$ are the basis spectra for α -helical, turn and non-regular structures. A typical CD spectrum of HSA-6-MP system has shown in Fig. 4, which gives an idea about the addition of 6-MP on the secondary structure of HSA. The helical content calculated by Sochacka *et al.* for HSA alone at pH 7.4 was found to be 55.0%. The CD parameter at the wavelength 222 nm of the spectrum of HSA is proportional to the α -helix content. Hence, the decrease or increase in the negative value of this parameter corresponds to changes of α -helix secondary structure of the protein and may provide direct information on the binding interaction and the formation of the ligand-protein complex. Here, the influence of the 6-MP on the secondary structure of the HSA was studied by CD spectra in far-UV region. Due to addition of 6-MP in HSA solution, the negative band intensities at 222 nm decreased relative to the spectra in the absence of 6-MP. The helical content decreased from ~ 55 to $\sim 53\%$ at low concentration of 6-MP (molar ratio HSA : 6-MP, 1 : 1) and to $\sim 50\%$ at higher concentration of 6-MP (molar ratio HSA : 6-MP, 1 : 5) (Fig. 4, Table 2). They explained the fact by the presence of 6-MP altered the secondary structure of the protein with a loss of α -helical stability due to 6-MP-HSA complex formation. From these

Table 2. Secondary structure components of HSA in native state and in presence of 6-MP³⁰

Secondary structural elements of a HSA	HSA	HSA+6-MP (1 : 1 complex)	HSA+6-MP (1 : 5 complex)
α -Helix (%)	55.0	53	50
Antiparallel (%)	4.4	4.5	4.9
Parallel (%)	4.7	5.3	5.7
β -Turn (%)	13.6	14	14.2
Random coil (%)	20.8	21.6	23.6

studies Sochacka *et al.* concluded that, the secondary structure of HSA after addition of 6-MP was also predominantly α -helix, but it becomes partially disordered with the loss of helical content^{30,44}. No CD spectra were found to be performed for BSA-6-MP system.

2.7. Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) :

Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) relies on

the distance-dependent transfer of energy from a donor molecule to an acceptor molecule. Due to its sensitivity to distance, FRET has been used to investigate molecular interactions. It is the radiationless transmission of energy from a donor molecule to an acceptor molecule. The donor molecule (here, BSA) is the chromophore that initially absorbs the energy and the acceptor (here, 6-MP) is the chromophore to which the energy is subsequently transferred. A transfer of energy could take place through a direct electrodynamic interaction between the primarily excited molecule and its neighbors, which will take place under conditions : (i) the donor can produce fluorescence light; (ii) fluorescence emission spectrum of the donor and UV-Vis absorbance spectrum of the acceptor have more overlap; and (iii) the distance between the donor and the acceptor is approached and is lower than 8 nm⁴⁵. Using FRET, the distance between 6-MP and BSA could be calculated by the equations^{34,37,43} :

$$E = \frac{R_0^6}{r_0^6 + R_0^6} \quad (15)$$

$$E = 1 - \frac{F_0}{F} \quad (16)$$

where, E denotes the efficiency of energy transfer between the donor and the acceptor, and R_0 is the critical distance when the efficiency of transfer is 50%.

$$R_0^6 = 8.79 \times 10^{-25} K^2 n^{-4} \Phi J \quad (17)$$

In the above equation K^2 is the orientation factor related to the geometry of the donor and acceptor of dipoles, and $K^2 = 2/3$ for random orientation as in fluid solution; n is the average refracted index of the medium in the wavelength range where spectral overlap is significant; Φ is the fluorescence quantum yield of the donor; and J is the effect of the spectral overlap between the emission spectrum of the donor and the absorption spectrum of the acceptor (Fig. 5), which could be calculated by the equation :

$$J = \frac{\sum F(\lambda)\epsilon(\lambda)\lambda^4 \Delta\lambda}{\sum F(\lambda)\Delta\lambda} \quad (18)$$

where, $F(k)$ is the corrected fluorescence intensity of the donor in the wavelength range from λ to $(\lambda + \Delta\lambda)$; $\epsilon(\lambda)$ is the extinction coefficient of the acceptor at λ . For BSA

system, $\Phi \sim 0.15^{27}$. Hence by putting the values in the above mentioned equation, one can have the J , R_0 , E , r values, depending on the value of n (refractive index), which will depend upon the medium. Some calculated values are given in Table 3. From the values it is clear that the energy transfer from BSA to 6-MP occurs with high probability. No result found for HSA-6-MP system.

Fig. 5. Spectral overlap of (a) BSA fluorescence, (b) with 6-MP absorption²⁷.

Table 3. Parameters for Förster energy transferring

No.	Reference No.	J ($\text{cm}^3 \text{L mol}^{-1}$)	R_0 (nm)	E	r (nm)
1.	27	1.21×10^{-14}	2.60	0.12	3.63
2.	26	2.03×10^{-15}	1.79	5.83 (%)	2.85

2.8. Molecular Docking :

The studies of protein binding to ligand by molecular docking are important and plays a major role to explain the relationship between the structure of ligand (drug molecule) and the function of protein from a theoretical viewpoint. This is helpful for practical applications in medicine. The interaction of HSA with 6-mercaptopurine (6-MP) was explained by Sochacka *et al.* in more than one paper^{30,46,47}. They performed the experiment with the program, Molegno Virtual Docker (MVD). They conclude that interaction and hydrogen bonding interaction. The 6-MP was located within binding cavity of subdomain IIA^{46,47} and the space occupied by site markers overlapped with that of 6-MP and the association constant for 6-MP was found to be : 4.48 ($\log_{\text{exp}}^{\text{HSA}} = 4.48$)³⁰.

Moreover, docking of 6-MP molecules in solution at pH = 7.4 included the docking of both neutral and an-

ionic forms at a time. The experiment revealed at least two binding sites of 6-MP in HSA structure. The binding sites of 6-MP were found to be in domain II (cavity : 1, primary binding site), and in the channel formed by domain I and III (cavity : 2, secondary binding site). From studies, Sochacka *et al.* concluded that, both forms of 6-MP exhibited higher interaction with HSA at site in cavity : 1 (primary binding site) than at site in cavity : 2 (secondary binding site). They also revealed that, in neutral form of 6-MP, the binding force was mainly hydrophobic interaction; whereas, hydrogen bond and electrostatic interaction were involved in case of anionic form of 6-MP^{46,47}. No information about docking of 6-MP with BSA was found.

Conclusion

6-MP is a well known anticancer drug and hence interaction of this with SA, the transport protein of living system is important. Several researchers had already performed experiment with SA and 6-MP^{26-30,46,47}. Our review mainly aims to highlight the culmination of observations found by them.

We have checked mainly spectroscopic technique and docking studies. From fluorescence quenching data, it has been found that 6-MP primarily interacts via the dynamic mechanism but minor contribution from static mechanism is also discerned. Thermodynamic parameters obtained from fluorescence data had pointed towards a dominance of hydrophobic interaction. CD data has revealed a change in secondary structure while docking data had justified the hydrophobic interaction found from fluorescence data and the site has been found to be mainly domain II.

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